

Appendix A

Table A.1. Start and end date of the recorded sightings of humpback whales between 2003 and 2019 for which the spatial reference, or position, was also registered.

#	Season	First record with spatial reference	Last record with spatial reference	Total number of records with spatial reference
1	2003-04	January 30, 2004	May 31, 2004	294
2	2004-05	January 21, 2005	April 13, 2005	399
3	2005-06	23 January, 2006	April 16, 2006	351
4	2006-07	January 12, 2007	April 25, 2007	674
5	2007-08	February 7, 2008	April 29, 2008	505
6	2008-09	January 8, 2009	April 25, 2009	339
7	2009-10	January 18, 2010	April 26, 2010	396
8*	2010-11	December 11, 2010	May 14, 2011	0
9*	2011-12	December 20, 2011	May 8, 2012	0
10	2012-13	December 19, 2012	June 1, 2013	391

11*	2013-	November 21, 2013	May 2, 2014	0
	14			
12*	2014-	December 12, 2014	May 16, 2015	0
	15			
13	2015-	November 28, 2015	April 26, 2016	909
	16			
14**	2016-	December 4, 2016	June 8, 2017	0
	17			
15*	2017-	November 24, 2017	May 6, 2018	0
	18			
16*	2018-	November 28, 2018	May 30, 2019	0
	19			

* Spatial reference or coordinates weren't recorded.

** "Position" as description referring to different reference points.

Table A.2. Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values for the GLMM to test the relationship between the top 5 ranked predictor variables and humpback whale abundance.

	Distance to 100-metre isobath	Distance to 200-metre isobath	Log spring chlorophyll	Log summer chlorophyll	Distance to marine traffic	Sea surface temperature	Log summer chlorophyll (squared)	Log sea surface temperature (squared)
VIF value	4.21	6.23	1.74	7.56	1.95	1.6	5.2	1.37

Table A.3. Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values for the GLMM to test the relationship between the top 5 ranked predictor variables and humpback whale abundance.

	Distance to 100- metre isobath	Log spring chlorophyll	Log summer chlorophyll	Distance to marine traffic	Sea surface temperature	Log summer chlorophyll (squared)	Log sea surface temperature (squared)
VIF value	2.15	1.73	6.33	1.82	1.13	4.83	1.07

Figure A.1. Sectors in which systematic whale watching effort took place (1. Punta Carrera - Galant; 2. Rupert - Carlos III; 3. Paso Inglés - Tortuoso; 4. Charles - Bárbara; 5. Seno Ballena; 6. Canal Jerónimo; and 7. Rest of ocean).

The effort is given in terms of hours per kilometer, corresponding to the length of the transects carried out in each sector, throughout the nine seasons included in this study.

Figure A.2. Photographs taken with a Nikon digital reflex camera, using a lens of 80-400 mm zoom, during the 2014-2015 feeding season. These pictures show the features used to identify humpback whales' individuals, such as shape of fins, coloration patterns and markings on the dorsal fin and fluke.

Figure A.3. Quadrants of 500x500 meters in which the presence and abundance of humpback whales was recorded during most feeding seasons between 2003 and 2019.

Figure A.4. Visual inspection of Sea surface temperature outliers in ArcGIS Pro highlighting temperature values higher than 13°C in the red circle (A), and comparison of histograms before transformation of these values to NA (B) and after said transformations (C).

Figure A.5. Visual inspection of summer chlorophyll outliers in ArcGIS Pro highlighting summer chlorophyll values higher than 20 mg/m^3 in red circles, which did not seem isolated (A), and comparison of histograms before the log transformation (B) and after said transformation (C).

Figure A.6. Visual inspection of spring chlorophyll outliers in ArcGIS Pro showing values higher than 20 mg/m^3 , which did not seem isolated from the rest (A), and comparison of histograms before the log transformation (B) and after said transformation (C).

Figure A.7. Visual inspection of marine traffic outliers in ArcGIS Pro showing values of higher than 20 active satellite hours in red circles (A), and comparison of histograms before turning the highlighted values to NA and applying a log transformation (B) and after said transformations (C).

Figure A.8. Histogram of the distance to marine traffic values.